

1 **Identification of differentially expressed transcripts in black women with HER2+ breast cancer.**

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7 We identified genes on the X chromosome, genes proximal to the genomic locus encoding HER2
8 (ERBB2), and genes residing on 1p12 among those whose expression is most different in patients with
9 HER2+ breast cancer when comparing tumor transcriptome based on genetic background (race). SPDYE
10 genes (including SPDYE2b and SPDYE6) molecules we previously described as genes that describe
11 TNBC in black women were also highly differentially expressed in HER2+ breast cancer in black women.
12 Protocadherins were activated and enriched in the tumors of black women with HER2+ breast cancer;
13 these included *PCDH10* and *PCDHB3*. A solute carrier *SLC31A1*, guidance receptor *Epha7*, and a
14 previously undescribed gene LOC107986334 were also among those whose expression defined HER2+
15 breast cancer in black women.
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